

DESIGNING FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS

WITH INSIGHT FROM BONE

R. W. McLay
Professor
Mechanical Engineering
University of Vermont
Burlington, Vermont 05401

M. C. Murphy
Assistant Professor
Department of Engineering & Technology
Norwich University
Northfield, Vermont 05663

M. H. Pope
Assistant Professor
Mechanical Engineering and
Orthopaedic Surgery
University of Vermont
Burlington, Vermont 05401

SUMMARY

A review is made of the biomechanics literature describing biological optimization, with a special emphasis on bone. The apparent design method of nature is discussed and placed in perspective with a design method for man-made composite materials, which is seen to be similar to the prototype/test method procedures of the aerospace industry. It is seen that optimization methods of nature are based strongly on the environment and feedback mechanisms. Approaches for copying these methods are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The design of composite structures progresses in every case study to some form of optimization, be it for cost, strength-to-weight ratio, or fracture toughness, to name but a few principal variables. Classical optimization theory concentrates on the minimization or maximization of a functional (e.g., cost, weight, fracture toughness) which is dependent on a number of variables, and which is usually subject to a number of constraints. (See for example Venkayya et al. [1973] and Khot et al. [1973]). These constraints imply conditions appended to the functional with Lagrange multipliers that ultimately destroy the minimum or maximum principle outside of a local region of the space studied. However, an even more serious practical limitation exists for our present methods of composite material optimization; the procedure is essentially an open-loop process.

With the present formulation of composite structure optimization problems we acquire sufficient information about the structural environment to identify the constraints and the primary variable to be optimized. The latter is oftentimes established arbitrarily. Once the design progresses toward its conclusion it is difficult to change direction. Thus, it can be considered as an open-loop process. This is in direct contrast to nature's design process for bone, a composite material; that process is closed-looped with a feedback mechanism.

An example applicable to composite structural optimization is presented by Richards [1965]. He discusses the use of Michell structures:

"The designer of structures is ultimately required to minimize the cost of the both fabrication and operation. For many applications, a reduction of structure weight will improve economics in both respects. Thus, a minimization of structure weight may be regarded as a valid primary objective of structural design."

Obviously, the ideal composite structure as viewed from the standpoint of the Michell structure can almost never be built; the constraints involved are simply too difficult to satisfy. Even if we could somehow ascertain the ideal orientation and prestress of every fiber in the structure it would be impossible with present technology to align them, prestress them, and fabricate the matrix around them. Technology has progressed only to such things as filament wound pressure vessels, uni-axial composites, etc. (See for example Langley [1973]).

In this paper we first review biological optimization, the apparent design scheme of nature's composite materials. Following this we examine a design for man made composite structures closely allied to that apparent in nature. In particular, we note that a knowledge of system loads, a knowledge of fundamental modes of failure (and associated analysis techniques), and rapid feedback mechanisms for recording of loads and failures are essential to this design process.

BIOLOGICAL OPTIMIZATION

Nature appears to approach the problem of composite structure optimization with a great deal of patience. Ideally, there is an infinite budget available and a very long lead time in the range of several hundred million years. In order to understand these methods of nature we examine certain recent papers in which the mechanisms of biological processes are discussed. Our emphasis of course is on the design of bone structures.

Tobin [1968] presents a great deal of information on the femoral bone structures of various mammals, reptiles, and birds. He reviews the basic statement of Wolff's law:

"Every change in the form and function of a bone or their function alone, is followed by certain definite changes in their bone architecture, and equally definite secondary alterations in their external conformaton, in accordance with mathematical laws."

In brief, the original paper by Wolff [1869] points to the evolution of the animal bone structure, both in the transmission of characteristics to the next generation and through "feed back" mechanisms altering the structure of the living animal itself. One could wax eloquent about a composite engineering material with this property. It is likely that if certain gene combinations appear to produce a structure identical to that produced by mechanical factors, it would be advantageous and thus retained by the population (See Simpson [1953]).

Chedd [1972] discusses some primitive concepts of fracture mechanics with regard to the energy dissipation mechanism in bone and natural membranes. Pope and Outwater [1972a], [1972b] have determined the fracture energy of bone and have also demonstrated the variation of mechanical properties as a function of position and orientation in a long bone as shown in Figure 1. (See Pope and Outwater [1974], where the optimization of

these properties appears to vary according to the loads imposed. Pope and Murphy [1974] have also shown that bone has good fracture properties because of its energy dissipation mechanisms as illustrated in Figure 2. The concept of optimization of the structure is implicit in these discussions. However, the question is "What is the functional being optimized?" It appears that nature does not always go for the maximum strength to weight found in a Michell structure. Indeed, for some animals the mechanism that dissipates energy in bone fracture may constitute the primary variable being optimized.

McMahon [1973] discusses the limitations of various living organisms by heat production, buckling, and bending. Referencing 26 previous publications and personal communications, he points out that, since an animal must have a structure capable of bearing its own weight, limited by bending and buckling constraints, and since its metabolic rate is strongly dependent on its surface area, it has restrictions placed on other factors in its development. Thus, we see nature at work optimizing the organism as a whole, as a system, subject to the constraints placed on it by thermodynamics and mechanics.

After Pope and Outwater [1974]

Figure 1: Variation of Fracture Strength as a Function of Distance from Epiphyses

After Pope and Murphy [1974]

Figure 2: Opening Mode Causing Pull out of Osteons

Let us distinguish between bone and bones, i.e., between the composite material and the composite structure. The distribution of the bone material in the structure differs enormously in different animals that are subjected to widely varying loads. Sir D'Arcy Thompson's [1917] classic work discusses the calcis of various animals. It is pointed out how the trabeculae or struts of bone correspond to the lines of tensile and compressive stress. Similarities are noted between the homo sapiens and the bear. But, in the bear, more powerful trabeculae transmit the load forward to the toes rather than through the heel to the ground, reflecting the less perfect upright posture of the bear. Similarly, in the leopard we see the effect of digitigrade, i.e., tip toe, progression. There, the tuberosity (hind part) of the heel is more of a lever than a pillar with compression and tensile members in distinctly opposite bundles. Perhaps the most beautiful example of nature's optimization is the metacarpal bone of the vulture, shown schematically in Figure 3. Viewed in one plane it is the Warren truss so beloved of aeronautical engineers. However, nature has developed the V-shaped struts in a three-dimensional configuration with obvious structural advantage.

After Prochnow in D'Arcy [1917]

Figure 3: Metacarpal Bone from a Vulture's Wing

Let us consider bone as a material. It is well known that bone growth responds to the stresses on it. The classical experiments of Sédillot, as discussed by D'Arcy Thompson, are an example. In his experiments the greater part of the tibia of young dogs was excised, leaving the fibula intact. Under normal mechanical loads the fibula, normally $1/6$ the diameter of the tibia, increased to the normal size of the tibia. How does such adaption take place? It is known that bone growth and destruction is under the control of osteocytes (bone cells). These differentiate into osteoblasts (bone builders) or osteoclasts (bone eaters). Also, it is known that bone is piezoelectric (See Bassett [1965]) and it is thought that the osteons, which are analagous to the fibers in a composite, grow or are absorbed in the matrix of the composite, mucopolysaccharide, according to signals generated by the piezoelectric effect.

The picture that we view then is that of nature as a Monte Carlo process, trying composite structural materials continually around the design of a specific animal, modifying the structure to adapt the animal to its environment and allowing only those structures best

adapted to the environment to propagate to future generations. We next examine such a design process for man-made composite materials.

A DESIGN PROCESS

Classical optimization techniques are complex and difficult to apply for optimal design of composite materials, at least, that is what the evidence from nature implies. In order to optimize the material or the structure we must first decide what to optimize and what constraints are present. Indeed, there may be two or more variables that must be optimized simultaneously while satisfying other constraints. However, it appears that nature optimizes according to a very simple rule:

"Arrange the variables such that the structure (and the animal) survives most often in its environment."

This suggests that probability will play a strong role in the design process.

In order to illustrate this we examine the plot shown in Figure 4, a schematic of the probability of structural survival of two extreme classes of animals. We note that only two variables are considered, the strength/weight ratio and impact toughness, and that the information in Figure 4 represents judgements made using previous literature and engineering experience. The figure illustrates quite clearly that nature optimizes the structure of a class of animals according to their behavior in their environment. A bird will, in general, flee from combat, its skeletal structure being optimized toward a maximum strength/weight ratio (again, the vulture's metacarpal). Hence, we might assume that a bird of a certain class has a high probability of structural survival clustered about a point on the plane. At the same time, its structure must have some impact toughness; however, what it has contrasts sharply with that of the other animal considered, a land animal.

A survivable land animal of a certain class is in general a combative animal. Thus, we assume that it will have a high probability of structural survival clustered about a second point on the plane where the impact toughness is a value that supports combat. Of course the land animal must have a sufficient strength/weight ratio as well, but it will not approach that of the bird.

Figure 4: Probabilities of Structural Survival

Let us view our design process in the same light as that apparent in nature. We start with a very primitive method for composite structural design with the following steps:

1. Devise a trial structure.
2. Place the structure in service and wait for failure.
3. Examine the failure and redesign the structure accordingly.
4. Replace the structure and return to step 2.

The reader will note immediately 1) the cost of such a procedure, 2) the lead times involved, and 3) the safety questions so ominously present in the case of a primary structural member of an aerospace vehicle. However, the procedure, with some modifications, can be identified as the present design procedure for aircraft, where we find a costly prototype and a careful test program. The four steps can also be identified as an

optimization procedure, however slow and painstaking, although it is very difficult to recognize any aspects of classical optimization.

In order to make the above procedure feasible we must provide the capability to obtain the following information:

1. The system load prediction.
2. The fundamental modes of failure predictions with associated analysis techniques.
3. The rapid feedback of information.

The description of loads as random variables is probably the most difficult of all of the tasks, especially in the design of a new aerospace structure. We must obtain adequate information about the environment in which the structure operates. Unfortunately, a complete knowledge of the fundamental modes of failure of composite structures is not yet available; many of the mechanisms cannot be described at present since they are still subjects of controversy. In addition, all of these failure effects are nonlinear and thus simplifications such as Gaussian response to Gaussian excitation for a linear system found in random vibrations are not applicable. The situation is further confused by the many failure modes of a composite material. For example, a common failure of a composite material is through the propagation of a crack through:

1. The matrix.
2. The fiber.
3. The fiber/matrix interface.

We know that the first law of thermodynamics governs the dissipation of energy through the crack extension. However, it is still not clear how the crack path is determined.

Feedback of information is also important to the design process. As mentioned previously, Bassett [1965] describes the remarkable ability of bone to react to a new environment through the feedback of a signal from a piezoelectric effect. The bone actually remodels itself according to the loads it feels. Evidence of these effects is presented by Burstein, Currey, Frankel, Heiple, Lunsett, and Vessely [1972], where animal experiments revealed the stress concentration effects of screw holes gradually being diminished.

Obviously, to produce a man-made composite structure that heals itself is a tall order, although paints now exist that can heal scratches on a surface. However, a great deal of work has been done to instrument composite materials for recording information. For example, Reifsnider and Williams [1974] report a method for studying heat emission due to fatigue damage to composite materials. Henneke, Herakovich, Jones, and Renieri [1975] show a method for analyzing failure of a composite by recording the acoustic emission. Dally and Panizza [1972] and Panizza and Dally [1973] discuss the use of conducting polymers as fatigue damage indicators. Troke [1973] presents a review of strain-gage instrumentation methods for flight testing. Thus, the literature indicates that methods are becoming available for obtaining rapid feedback of information during tests and actual service of the structure.

DISCUSSION

We have reviewed the literature in biomechanics describing biological optimization, with a special emphasis on the design of bone. From this we have attempted to deduce the design method of nature, which appears to be a gigantic Monte Carlo process, making trials (i.e., mutations) about a central design and searching for a better bone structure with each trial. A design process for man-made composite structures is then described and seen to be similar to the prototype and test methods currently in use by the aerospace industry. The key points of the work are:

1. Nature optimizes a composite structure according to the details of the environment and may choose an unusual primary variable to ensure structural survival.
2. In order to copy nature's design method we must be able to better describe the system loads, have a far better knowledge of the modes of failure of the composite, have available adequate analysis tools, and implement techniques for rapidly recording and interpreting the actual loads and structural failures.

We have not yet achieved these goals but, once identified, they become a series of ideals toward which we can work.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was partially funded by AFOSR Grant 74-2734 (Energy Methods for Optimal Design of Composite Structures) and AFOSR Grant 74-2738 (Biomechanics and Radiologic Studies of the Lumbar Spine).

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